

UNIVERSITI BRUNEI DARUSSALAM (UBD)

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Multiple Case Analysis

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1.0 Problem Statement

1.1 Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)

One of the world's most frequent challenges is the ability of NGOs to sustain their financial funds for their long-term projects (Rehema, 2014). NGOs require money to implement and maintain programs. Like other NGOs, SCOT often depends on sponsorships and donations from the public for regular operations. Financial instability renders it impossible for SCOT to provide a broad fund base and not relying exclusively on contributions from governments and private organizations.

Contributions from international states or multinational organizations are often challenging to procure, because contributions from certain nations may provide their own clauses that clash with national principles. Therefore, it is difficult to raise funds for projects and programs. Anwar seeks to rise additional funding to cover the expenses of each project / event with adequate money; nevertheless, it finds it impossible to get enough funding to develop the whole organization. Financial aid is seldom provided and in-kind help is more common, such as free usage of facilities and professional aid.

In order to accomplish the goal of SCOT and 'resource mobilization' Anwar needed to consider more efficient and creative ways to finance their initiatives. The mobilization of capital is a mechanism in which both financial and non-fund capital are mobilized either internationally or internally to help operational operations (Rehema, 2014). In addition to externally generated financial capital, the company may often produce money internally. The project should be coordinated and funds received, in-kind gifts earned and revenue produced by the organization of fee-paying conferences, seminars and volunteers. SCOT therefore needs to pursue alternative financing mechanisms to maintain financial viability without jeopardizing its target.

SCOT organized the Youth against Poverty Workshop (YAP) in 2016 for the first time in the year. This was a three-day project for SCOT staff and their workers, including scholars and civic members. The business has also provided funding from many organizations, including Progresif Cellular, Universiti Brunei Darussalam, Ajwa Kitchen and Bake Culture Brunei. The workshop was restricted to 30 local participants aged 19 to 27 and BND 25 per person. The primary emphasis was on teaching and introducing young people to the challenges of poverty, analytical thought and an ability to discuss potential ideas through the execution of the project. At the same moment, it also started the Green Xchange initiative to provide financial help.

1.2 Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV)

Leslie Chiang founded Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV) to contribute both to the socio-economic gains and to environmental conservation. But Leslie Chiang encountered numerous obstacles in making this ecotourism industry a success. All was originally made up of natural materials because in the village plastics and clothes were prohibited. The products and resources of the forest such as bamboos and trees have been used; over time they have deteriorated and replaced numerous times before the owner has chosen to replace them with a new type of resources to eliminate pollution by saving and restoring the natural ingredients. Brunei's atmosphere does not

permit such developments. Moisture kills the building and the salinity of the water quickly erodes the products. SEV has also encountered difficulties in Brunei in hiring and attracting ecotourism skills to improve their goods and services.

Ecotourism is a fairly new way to do tourism in Brunei. There is a severe lack of qualified staff. To support and achieve the project of SEV, the benefit of providing more experience and well-versed green company businessmen is crucial. Another obstacle faced by SEV is the rivalry from other nearby retreats such as Miri and Sarawak. This retreat is sponsored not only by more local but also by international staff. They may deliver more creative and sustainable events which are more affordable and appealing to visitors.

In the future, more infrastructures are also expected. Currently, there are just 10 beds in the tents and in the future they expect to build 30 beds. In turn, Leslie Chiang aims to enhance travelers' forest camping experience. The need for jungle camping is strong and they want to make the customers in a jungle-like environment feel comfortable. Sumbiling Eco Village is also part of Leslie's potential plans to provide local and also foreign schools with awareness about the ancient Iban community as well as nature protection.

Increased tourism to vulnerable natural resources will endanger the dignity of local communities and habitats without proper preparation and maintenance. The growth in visits to environmentally vulnerable areas will contribute to significant environmental deterioration. Likewise, the introduction of international tourists and resources will influence local populations and indigenous cultures in various ways. Furthermore, temperature changes, currency exchange rates and political and social factors will render overreliance on tourism a risky sector. Nevertheless, it offers biodiversity and local economies important incentives. Ecotourism may generate significant revenue from other sources for the conservation of the Brunei national parks and other natural areas. In addition, ecotourism will provide local community with few other income-generating opportunities for viable economic growth. Furthermore, ecotourism will raise travelers' degree of awareness and advocacy and make them more active and successful conservation officers.

1.3 BruTEL Cellular

To stop mountain papers and prevent traffic congestion and reduce travel time from workplace to bank or post office, more Bruneians prefer electronic transactions. Nonetheless, the proportion of users who are less reactive to these improvements still exists, especially senior citizens who are comparatively less technically savvy.

As Communications and Media Manager, Jamilah knew that BruTEL's e-filling system is going to lose a segment of its current users and potential users, as older citizens still prefer traditional payment to e-filling. She wondered how to solve this problem.

Some of the key factors that consumers are unable to accept paper bills are the recall. Some customers, especially older generations, who are used to making their monthly payments with their paper bills. There is considerable fear that if you do not have the actual account as a visible indicator, a charge becomes likely to skip.

Another issue is the exhaustion in customers' passwords. The situation involves the retention of countless passwords by customers of all ages to access several online portals, and each account can have different requirements — all in the name of security.

In comparison, registration can be seen as a tedious operation. Firstly, BruTEL will be involved in e-billing and paperless software. Secondly, BruTEL needs its customers to complete their e-bill registration.

Registration may be ineffective if consumers encounter a complicated registration procedure.

Such problems encapsulate BruTEL's problem of rendering consumers paperless or e-filing. BruTEL aims at identifying ways to improve e-bills and paperless adoption and designing successful communication campaigns that enable BruTEL meet its growth goals in favor of BruTEL's billing and payment solutions. BruTEL users lately have been able to pay their bills, buy digitally and transfer money abroad with the latest BruTEL E-Wallet mobile wallet program.

2.0 Case Analysis

2.1 Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)

According to Dhananjayan (2015) only about 1% of all official funding, and far fewer of all international support, goes directly to the south of the country. Unpublished surveys of private foundations often show that they channel much of their support in the global north into what he calls "fundermediaries." Although more resources are gradually sought for southern performers, this method of "trickle down" generates inefficiencies and undermines the organization.

Their annual Civil Society State Report based this year on civil society capital. In the weeks leading up to and after then, he asked almost every donor why they appear unable or unable to fund the frontline directly. Here are the five main explanations they gave him:

1. Many Southern and smaller NGOs are not able to fill in any of their forms and invest their money effectively.
2. They are not able to give smaller amounts of money administratively.
3. They have to funnel capital into a variety of trustworthy stakeholders to handle costs and conform to their own laws.
4. It has stringent anti-terrorism and anti-money laundering laws that render it explicitly challenging to send.
5. They are under domestic political strain to fund their nation through NGOs.

2.2 Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV)

According to a bloggers, he said that one of the reasons that it is hard to find skilled workers is because it is hard to learn a trade.

Let's consider what skilled means. It implies that you should do anything that needs at least some experience. This varies from washing dishes to operating on a face.

Understanding how to function on the core takes a long time and calls for dedication, not to mention resources. Not everybody has the resources to devote time or energy into their job. This is why you shouldn't mess or know how to perform the job with the next century.

It takes little time to learn to clean dishes. It normally takes only a month to get a good washing pace. Then the person is able to do that skillfully. The question is that only people are eager to practice their profession.

This is for the new skilled work on the market. What about the retired professional workers? They're not let go. They're not let go. They are ultimately an individual in whom investments have been made.

Industries need to realize that recruiting a new professional worker is a pain in the butt. You need not only an individual who wants to read, but also an individual who understands how. A professional electrician needs a trainee who knows how to fish out some wire or how to clean dust away.

But what if the trainee leaves? You have missed a guy with which you invested time. And it's time for capital. Organizations also want to retain employees worth their time to prepare people who wish to work for them.

2.3 BruTEL Cellular

According to a report from AITI's Household ICT Survey (2016), one factor why living without paper is a challenge is that certain citizens often have the need for a paper bill to inform them they have paid their bills or have not paid it.

Statistics suggest that in internet banking the overall number of young and working people aged between 15 and 54 has been 33 percent, while in senior citizens aged between 55 and 65, it has been found to equate to 18 percent (AITI Household ICT Study, 2016). The figures also indicate that the share of the elderly is greater than that of youth and employed people with a disparity of 15%. If it comes to e-mails, it is normal to collect e-boxes or e-statements, figures indicate that young people had a high of 57 percent, while for the aged or seniors; it was 37 percent that indicated that there is a greater utilization of the aged. These numbers represent practices that use machines for the usage of mobile devices, which is popular too many people use internet banking applications like BIBD online or Baiduri Banking Apps, while it is projected that young people and working people are 36% and 16% respectively for senior citizens.

Furthermore, 72% and 22% for youth and working people as well as senior citizens give and receive e-mails respectively. The small share of internet use among senior citizens may be due to the fact, in view of the complexities of the use of technologies, that senior citizens are reluctant to use such platforms. It is also clear that this will not be helpful to older people because the figures often refuse to take note of the reality that they are assisted to utilize the facility. Furthermore, this might not be beneficial for senior citizens, particularly as their increasing perceptions of technology have been stated.

3.0 Alternatives Solution

3.1 Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)

As mentioned above Anwar had give out a few solution for the financial problem that they are facing and they are the organized the Youth against Poverty Workshop (YAP) in 2016 for the first time in the year. This was a three-day project for SCOT staff and their workers, including scholars and civic members. The business has also provided funding from many organizations, including Progresif Cellular, Universiti Brunei Darussalam, Ajwa Kitchen and Bake Culture Brunei. The workshop was restricted to 30 local participants aged 19 to 27 and BND 25 per person. The primary emphasis was on teaching and introducing young people to the challenges of poverty, analytical thought and an ability to discuss potential ideas through the execution of the project. At the same moment, it also started the Green Xchange initiative to provide financial help.

The advantages and disadvantages of Green Xchange are as follow:

Advantages

1. It helps to lessen the less fortunate.
2. To preserve the environment by collecting recyclable items from resident of Kampong Ayer.
3. Able to induce the recycling habits to the resident of Brunei.
4. Youths involved in the project will continue to monitor the project, turning the good value into a Brunei culture.
5. Can help increase the understanding of handling government projects that require the involvement of the public through volunteers.

Disadvantages

1. Do not have the technology and skills to recycle, the recyclable.
2. Have difficulty in having enough people to make this projects go smoothly.

3.2 Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV)

Given the difficulties of eco-tourism promotion, Sumbiling Eco Village has made a significant contribution to the growth of knowledge and sustainable development in the district of Temburong. To attain and retain the green status of Sumbiling Eco Village, Leslie Chiang is dedicated to sustainable growth through its use of the area's green building program to facilitate the design, construction and refurbishment of buildings that use green building practices. Leslie Chiang is dedicated to developing Sumbiling Eco Village as a leader of sustainable ecotourism in Brunei or a green company, particularly a company which has minimal negative effects on the world's or local climate, the culture, society or the economy, a business that strives for the threefold outcome.

The advantages and disadvantages of eco-tourism are as follow:

Advantages

1. Provide Employment.
2. Improvement in transport system.
3. Publicity of Brunei.
4. Preservation of traditional and cultural heritage.
5. Restoration of historical buildings for tourist.
6. Protect of natural environment.

Disadvantages

1. Increased in pollution.
2. Some revenue from tourism may leak out from the country due to foreign labor.
3. Increased in crime for some country, clash of local customs.

3.3 BruTEL Cellular

Jamilah knew that, for years, older generations had charged their expenses in every way. Thus, these older consumers will not readily consider the shift in procedure from physical purchase to e-filling. Jamilah thought that BruTEL needs to persuade its customers, particularly the elderly, to move from physical to online transactions. BruTEL wants to better encourage the value of the open usage of social media to push forward and enforce the ecological agenda. It may also help to build a campaign based on such CSR measures as 'going green,' 'enhanced protection,' or 'whole comfort.' When BruTEL can remove its consumers' hesitations and uneasiness in the 'go paperless,' BruTEL will continue to build plans or take steps to solve their problem.

The advantages and disadvantages of going paperless are as follow:

Advantages

1. Speed of Information

When all is digitally processed in computers, relative to paper, connectivity is simple and convenient. With only a few mouse clicks, staff, customers and business owners have access to all info, contracts and customer information. This removes the need to find the file or type that saves every time.

2. Mobile Workforce

Changing from paper to digital storage, particularly cloud technologies, makes holding information on the Web easier for mobile employees. There is further freedom to visit clients outside the workplace or to operate at home for a day. Employees can instantly and conveniently view relevant details electronically. Also, remote employees are not still employed in the same town as the company owner, and companies can have a different stream of potential.

3. Significant Cost Savings

Having it recorded as files is easier than copying and storing it on paper, or on disk drives, Flash disks or in cloud-based services. This reduces the risk of shredding facilities of records containing classified material. Few organizations provide whole rooms and holding centers for document archiving. This expense is reduced by paperless programs.

Disadvantages

1. Consumer Habits

Many companies have point-of-sale systems and do this on a tablet. While the business owner and his staff can perform purchases rapidly and easily, they can leave consumers worried about walking without the receipt of a report. Any customers want to analyze items on paper and don't want to print their company later.

2. Potential Hackers

Since evidence is preserved on paper and secured in the cabinets with paperwork, anyone will have physical access to documents to steal details. When all is physically handled, hackers don't have to think about it. Company owners are sometimes too busy upgrading applications and malware security to allow the deployment of spyware simpler for hackers to intercept details or hijack client information.

3. Hardware or Software Issues

Although all is digitally recorded, a device might crash and all knowledge will be lost. Make sure the details are backed up periodically to allow the recovery phase smoother. And, the same way as a power loss or an Internet system malfunction will delay activities, it also triggers a disruption of service to firms. In the case of an automated communication connectivity issue, company owners will provide backup plans.

4.0 Recommendation

The advice for all three organizations is to collaborate and encourage more awareness in order to gain further support for SCOT, and to allow employees who are worthy of approaching SEV and to know that other items such as bills will be accomplished without paper.

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